

Transcription of the Dynamic Validation Study: First Session

Artifact: Transcription of the first session of the dynamic validation

Moderator: Hugo Villamizar, PhD student of the Informatics Department at PUC-Rio

Subjects of the first session: One data scientist lead of Americanas S.A.

Date: 20/09/2022

This section presents an overview of the feedback coming from one data scientist lead who participated in the first session of the dynamic validation. It also contains the transcriptions and codes involved in this validation study.

Participants

Table II shows an overview of the participant characterization. It is noteworthy that the participant has been actively working with the development of ML-enabled systems at Americanas, having participated in 20 projects during the last eight years.

Table II

Id	Role	Project	Background	# year working with ML	# ML projects
P1	Data scientist lead	Product Classification	Linguistic - Computer Science	8	20

We used the column 'Id' of Table II to identify the participants and their opinions. The moderator (M) of the session was the first author of the paper. We highlighted with color green the part of the text which contributes to generating the codes.

We translated the focus group from Portuguese to English since the session was conducted in Portuguese with a Brazilian software practitioner. In the following, we present the transcriptions.

Discussion with the participants of the first session of the dynamic validation

Id	Comment	Code
M	First, thank you so much for being here. I'm going to start with a brief description of each perspective and its concerns. If you don't understand something, please let me know. You can interrupt me when you find it necessary.	
M	<i>[Here, the first perspective was introduced by the moderator: ML objectives]</i>	
P1	Before starting with the next perspective, I have one doubt. When are we going to decide if the problem we have is going to be tackled with ML techniques? In this perspective, can we know if a problem is suitable to be solved with ML techniques?	
M	<p>We consider that the point you mentioned is a feasibility study out of the scope of PerSpecML. We have a premise: before using our proposal a set of resources must be evaluated. For example, a reasonable amount of data, resources such as knowledge of the technologies involved with ML, people, money, among others.</p> <p>On second thought, by using our proposal, the stakeholders involved in the ML project could identify that there are unresolved concerns that make it difficult to start an ML project. For example, if there are difficulties in defining ML objectives, or if data-related concerns are not clearly resolved, then there are symptoms that the problem could not be solved with ML techniques. But initially this is not part of our scope.</p>	
P1	I ask this because ML is a fancy solution at first glance, that everyone wants to use. But maintaining and building systems with ML components is more complex than you might think.	
M	Yes, I totally agree. In fact, we seek to provide that overview so that the stakeholders can identify that landscape in the form of perspectives and concerns.	
M	<i>[Here, the second perspective was introduced by the moderator: user experience]</i>	
M	<i>[Here, the third perspective was introduced by the moderator: infrastructure]</i>	
P1	I have one doubt. When you say data streaming you are concerned with the data in operation or the data to train the model?	
M	In the data streaming concern we are concerned with the data in operation	
P1	Ok, I got it.	

P1	<p>In my opinion, you should consider the cost of the infrastructure as a concern. At Americanas, we have had several experiences where infrastructure-related cost drives ML solution architectures. We have two projects that reach the objectives but depending on the infrastructure we spend more or less money. The cost is super relevant for us.</p>	7) Improvements for our approach - cost as concern in the infrastructure perspective.
M	[Here, the fourth perspective was introduced by the moderator: model]	
M	[Here, the fifth perspective was introduced by the moderator: data]	
P1	Talking about data in ML contexts is very complex. I understand the data taxonomy divided into training, validation and test. But I feel a lack of definitions about the operational data, I mean, when do I know if the operational data represents the behavior of the model?	
M	In that sense, we have two concerns in the data perspective that can help: the completeness of the data that seeks to guarantee that data contains sufficient observations of all situations where the model will operate. On the other hand, we also have the real usage concern that is the need to get real data representing the real problem.	
M	[Here, the perspective-based ML task and concern diagram was introduced by the moderator]	
P1	<p>I would like to mention that the diagram does not consider an important stakeholder in all the process. That stakeholder is the domain expert. This role is extremely important because they are essential to help define good objectives and to analyze data. The domain expert cannot be left out.</p> <p>Many times I worked as a domain expert of ML projects. So, If this role is not modeling in the diagram, I could not use it. Do you understand my point?</p>	7) Improvements for our approach - consider other roles for PerSpecML.
M	Yes, I fully agree with your point. We will improve our proposal by adding the domain expert role.	
M	[Here, the specifications of the two projects derived from PerSpecML were presented by the moderator]	
M	Now we want to hear from you about PerSpecML and the specification we derived from it. What is your opinion about the proposal? Do you think that PerSpecML helped to specify the ML-enabled system?	
P1	<p>The proposal is very good. The diagram and the specification template will help us a lot. PerSpecML provides a more comprehensive overview and is far better than the ML canvas, which is the artifact we currently use to specify systems with ML components.</p>	04 - Positive position about our approach

		11 - Benchmarking of our approach - PerSpecML better than ML canvas
P1	On the practical use of the PerSpecML, there are many concerns that should be considered. It worries me to have to analyze so many aspects but at the same time I consider that the landscape that PerSpecML offers is very complete. My point is to what extent the solution becomes complex. In my opinion, the diagram can give a vision of what could be prioritized and analyzed first.	07 - Improvements for our approach - classification of the concerns.
M	Good point, we will provide some light about it. Thank you so much for pointing out this.	

In total, in this dynamic validation, we identified the following list of codes attached to the transcription.

- 04 - Positive position about our approach
- 07 - Improvements for our approach - cost as a new concern
- 07 - Improvements for our approach - consider other roles for PerSpecML
- 07 - Improvements for our approach - classification of the concerns
- 11 - Benchmarking of our approach - PerSpecML better than ML canvas.

Transcription of the Dynamic Validation Study: Second Session

Artifact: Transcription of the second session of the dynamic validation

Moderator: Hugo Villamizar, PhD student of the Informatics Department at PUC-Rio

Subjects of the second session: Two data scientists of Americanas S.A.

Date: 26/09/2022

This section presents an overview of the two practitioners who participated in the second session of the dynamic validation. It also contains the transcriptions and codes involved in this validation study.

Participants

Table III shows an overview of the participant characterization. It is noteworthy that both have been actively working with the development of ML-enabled systems at Americanas, having participated in at least 10 projects each.

Table III

Id	Role	Project	Background	# year working with ML	# ML projects
P2	Data Scientist	N/A	Computer Science	3	10
P3	Data Scientist lead	B	Economics	4	12

We used the column 'Id' of Table II to identify the participants and their opinions. The moderator (M) of the session was the first author of the paper. We highlighted with color green the part of the text which contributes to generating the codes.

We translated the focus group from Portuguese to English since the session was conducted in Portuguese with Brazilian software professionals. In the following, we present the transcriptions.

Discussion with the participants of the second session of the dynamic validation

Id	Comment	Code
M	We are so glad to have you all today to talk about PerSpecML and the specifications of the two projects we specified by using PerSpecML. First, I'm going to present a brief description of each perspective and its concerns. If you don't understand something, please let me know. You can interrupt me when you find it necessary.	
M	<i>[Here, the first perspective was introduced by the moderator: ML objectives]</i>	
M	<i>[Here, the second perspective was introduced by the moderator: user experience]</i>	
M	<i>[Here, the third perspective was introduced by the moderator: infrastructure]</i>	
M	Well, any questions or comments so far?	
P3	Yes, looking at the relationships I can see the following: linking the model update task in the infrastructure perspective with the need to get user feedback in the user experience perspective makes sense	04 - Positive position about our approach
P3	Another comment, we don't just have software engineers and data scientists here. We also have data engineers, ML engineers, and cloud engineers, who perform many of the tasks involved in this perspective. It may happen that other companies have a different functional organization and those stakeholders do not always apply. So, I think it would be good to make this clear.	07 - Improvements for our approach - consider other roles for PerSpecML
M	<i>[Here, the fourth perspective was introduced by the moderator: model]</i>	
P2	All the concerns you explained are good aspects we should analyze, but I think you are missing a concern in this perspective: Performance degradation is typically something that even data scientists don't discuss in ML projects. In fact, this is something that should be explained to customers because it is something that will affect them over time.	07 - Improvements for our approach - performance degradation as a new concern
M	Sure, it makes sense for us. Thank you for pointing this out.	
M	<i>[Here, the fifth perspective was introduced by the moderator: data]</i>	
M	Any questions or comments regarding the data perspective?	

M	<i>[Here, the specifications of the two projects derived from PerSpecML were presented by the moderator]</i>	
M	Thank you for paying attention and participating in the discussion. Now we want to hear from you about PerSpecML and the specification we derived from it. What is your opinion about the proposal? Do you think that PerSpecML helped to specify the ML-enabled system?	
P3	I'm very satisfied with the results of the specifications of both projects. Several concerns were addressed and this is really helpful. I am not sure if at the end the specifications are already sufficiently clear, but I can tell you what has been raised is reasonable and useful. Coming up with a clear specification requires refinements and increments	04 - Positive position about our approach
P3	In addition, many times in our projects some of these concerns are only addressed when it is clearly too late. I see the diagram as a roadmap that allows me to identify components that would not be identified without its use.	04 - Positive position about our approach
P2	I found the approach you proposed very useful. There are several tasks that at the beginning of the project do not concern our team, but that deserve to be analyzed for their relationships with others.	04 - Positive position about our approach
P2	Looking at the diagram of PerSpecML, it summarizes the work of various ML teams.	04 - Positive position about our approach
M	Do you think that PerSpecML can be useful in practice?	
P3	Absolutely yes. Currently, we use ML canvas to describe ML systems, but PerSpecML covers more elements, and helps analyze their relationships. In that sense, we would benefit from the approach. In addition, the results of the specification were positive, in my opinion.	11 - Benchmarking of our approach - PerSpecML better than ML canvas
M	Nice. P2, would you like to say something?	
P2	Yes. I see the diagram could be extremely helpful for novice data scientists or engineers since it gets an overview of the ML workflow. In my opinion, that is outstanding.	04 - Positive position about our approach
P2	However, I would like to suggest an improvement. it would be interesting to classify each concern by its importance. Why do I say this? Looking at the diagram I see too many concerns that maybe can be confused at a first sight.	07 - Improvements for our approach - classification of the concerns.

In total, in this dynamic validation, we identified the following list of codes attached to the transcription.

- 04 - Positive position about our approach
- 07 - Improvements for our approach - consider other roles for PerSpecML
- 07 - Improvements for our approach - performance degradation as a new concern
- 07 - Improvements for our approach - classification of the concerns
- 11 - Benchmarking of our approach - PerSpecML better than ML canvas.